

Effect of different sowing dates on yield and yield component of dry direct seeded rice in rainfed lowland at Lombok, West Nusa Tenggara

Lia Hadiawati^{1*}

¹Assessment Institute For Agricultural Technology
West Nusa Tenggara Province, Jalan Raya Peninjauan Narmada, Lombok Barat, West
Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia

*Corresponding author : lia.hadiawati@yahoo.co.id

ABSTRACT

Direct seeded is a rice cultivation system in rainfed areas that fully depend on rainfall with little access to supplementary irrigation. This study aimed to determine the effect of sowing date on yield and yield component of new improved variety Inpari-39 Agritan grown using dry direct seeded system in rainfed areas at Central Lombok – West Nusa Tenggara. On-farm experiment was designed with randomized block design which treated with four sowing dates treatment that ten days different from first sowing at October 20th (T0), followed by the second sowing on October 30th (T1), next on November 10th (T2), and the last on November 20th (T3), where three farmers' field were set as replication. The results showed that under dry direct seeded system, yield of Inpari-39 ranged between 5.2 t/ha (T3) to 6.3 t/ha (T2), or in average 5.82 t/ha that very close to its potential yield 5.89 t/ha. Although early rainy season (T2) indicated optimum sowing date, but there was no significant different to other sowing dates. At optimum sowing date in T2, Inpari-39 produced the highest number of panicle/m² and percentage of filled spikelet, also the longest panicle and plant height.

Keywords: sowing date, dry direct seeded, rainfed

INTRODUCTION

Growing high yielding rice varieties that tolerant to abiotic stress such as drought and flood is one of the strategies to adapt climate change impact. Some new improved rice varieties with superior characteristics that are known as amphibious varieties are released by Indonesian Rice Research Institute since 2015, i.e. Inpari-38, Inpari-39, Inpari-40, and Inpari 41 that are suitable to be grown in rainfed areas (Wahab et al., 2017). In addition to the selection of the right varieties, optimum growth and rice yield also depend on environmental factor, especially for the rainfed areas. One of environmental friendly rice cultivation systems under rainfed condition in Indonesia is direct seeded system. The direct seeded system that locally known as Gogorancah system is

commonly practised by farmers at Southern Lombok Island of West Nusa Tenggara (WNT) Province.

The most environmental friendly practice in dry direct seeded system is land preparation using zero tillage or minimum tillage methods where rice is seeded in dry condition and soil in submerged condition after entering active tillering stage growth. After harvesting rice, legumes such as soybean, green bean, lab-lab, and others pulses that able to fix nitrogen were grown as rotation crops both on monoculture or intercropping system. Moreover, second crop biomass is left to cover the land until next planting season. The practice of direct seeded rice in Lombok is in line with the principles of conservation agriculture by the FAO (2015). Kato and Katsura (2014) reported that the dry direct seeded system is more efficient in using water because rice grows under non-saturated condition. Furthermore, Fukai et al. (1998) reported that Laos and Thailand have adopted the dry direct seed system to improve rainfed productivity. Mostly it reduced risk of terminal drought stress, easier weeds control, lesser labour cost, and in turn reducing production cost (Laing et al., 2015).

In WNT Province, the harvested area of rainfed rice fluctuates following the rains pattern, but in general the trend is increasing. During 1997 to 2007, the harvest area increased from 25.197 hectares (ha) to 42.435 ha, and by 2016 become 62.108 ha (BPS, 2016). Total contribution of rainfed areas to total rice production at WNT Province was as much as 10.02%. According to Pandey et al. (2002), 18% of global rice production was produced from 28% similar cultivation practices from all over the world. Despite the increase of harvested area, rainfed rice productivity is still lower than irrigated rice. The yield gap between irrigated rice and rainfed rice is about 1.7 t/ha (Aggarwal et al., 2008).

Based on BPS data (2016), the productivity of rainfed rice at WNT Province ranged from 2.8-3.9 t/ha, while irrigated rice is generally in range of 4.6-5.9 t/ha. There was an improvement of rice productivity to range of 2.4-2.7 t/ha since last decade when new improved rice variety introduced (BPS, 2006). In 1975, the direct seeded rice yielded 5.06 t/ha using IR-26 variety in Indramayu and 5.60 t/ha using IR-36 variety in Nambahdadi-Lampung (Ismail and Effendy, 1975). The direct seeded system was brought to WNT Province around 1980-1981 under Supra-insus program (Fagi and Kartaatmadja, 2002). In 1994, direct seeded rice production under normal condition at Jakenan, Central Java was 6.0 t/ha (Budi and Suprihatno, 1994).

The main obstacle of rainfed rice is water availability that mostly depend on only rainfall. Therefore, the right planting time should be in line with the rainfall to avoid yield loss due to drought or flooding. Severe drought in Lombok Island during 1997-1998 impacted 8.400 ha rice field where 2.000 ha were damaged (Yasin et al., 2004). Budi and Suprihatno (1994) stated that the

main constrain of direct seeded system is variability of the onset and lack of rainfall before and after sowing. Effects of abiotic stress in rainfed rice are widely reported by researcher around the world. This study aims to determine the effect of different sowing dates on yield and yield components of new improved rice variety that tolerant to abiotic stress when grown under dry direct seeded systems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

On-farm experiments were carried out in rainfed lowland at Segala Anyar Village of Pujut Subdistrict - Central Lombok from October 2016 to March 2017. The field located at S 8047'05.25 "x E 116017'55.92" that 128 m above sea level. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with three replication having a gross plot size of 25 m². Zero tillage method was applied on land preparation with herbicide treatment at seven days before sowing. Dry seed of Inpari-39 was sown directly in the field with 20 cm spacing between row. Seed was sown on four different sowing dates at October 20th (T0), October 30th (T1), November 10th (T2), and November 20th (T3).

The improved rice variety known Inpari-39 agritan leased in 2015 is recommended for rainfed lowland areas to an altitude of 600 m above sea level (Wahab et al., 2017). Crop was fertilized with N, P, and K at recommended rate using Urea at dosage 200 kg/ha for twice application, and NPK-Phonska at dosage 100 kg/ha applied once with urea's first fertilizer. Plant maintenance such as weeding and pest/disease control were taken as necessary.

Initial result of Vertisols analysis showed high clay content (44%), 31% sand, and 24% silt. Soil acidity was neutral (7.52) and very high on C-organic content (28%), N-total (1.4%), and P (17.14 ppm), while K content (0.45 cmol/kg) and CEC (31.38 cmol/kg) were high (Eviati and Sulaeman, 2009).

Harvesting was done after crop in maturity stage growth. Five hills were taken randomly from each plot to measure parameters of plant height, number of tillers, percentage of productive tillers, panicle length, number of grains per panicle, percentage of filled grain, and 1000 weight grains. Harvested area of 6 m² of each plot was obtain to dry biomass weight and yield at 14% moisture content. Recorded data were analyzed statistically for variance different using STAR 2.0.1 (Statistic Tools for Agricultural Research). Difference among the treatment means were compared using least significant difference (LSD) test at 5 % probability level (STAR, 2014).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Climate variability

Monsoonal climate at WNT Province is affected by monsoon from Asia and Australia. The rainy season normally starts from October to March, followed by dry season from April to September. Climatic data during experiment are shown in Figure 1. During experiment (October 2016-February 2017), the average daily temperature was 26.92°C with an average minimum temperature range of 23.82°C and a maximum temperature of 31.70°C. The average solar radiation was 5.29 hours, and the average humidity was 85.40%. The amount of rainfall and rainy days for T0, T1, T2, and T3 from sowing to harvest were 1.179 mm and 86 days, 1.239 mm and 85 days, 1.292 mm and 87 days, and 1.264 and 81 days respectively.

Figure 1. Rainfall, solar radiation, temperature, and humidity for October 2016 to February 2017 period at Pujut subdistrict, Central Lombok -WNT

Yield and yield component

Grain yield of Inpari-39 was not significantly affected by sowing date, however the highest yield reached when seed sown at 10th November (6.28 t/ha) and the least yield sown at 20th November (T3). In average, Inpari-39 produced 5.82 t/ha grain at 14% moisture content, this average is very close its potential yield at 5.89 t/ha (Wahab et al., 2017). Although there was no significant difference between treatments, optimum sowing date at T2 will increase yield at about 17.2%. Inpari-39 shows a fairly good adaptability with climate and soil moisture dynamics during experiment.

Table 1 shows that there was decreasing trend in the grain yield in earlier sowing dates, from the highest at T2 (6.28 t/ha), followed by the T1 (6.20 t/ha) and the T0 (5.58 t/ha). The optimum sowing date (T2) was attributed to

more number of panicle/m², higher percentage of filled spikelet, and longer panicle. In contrast, delayed sowing date (T3) leads to unfavourable condition where weight of 1000-grains and panicle length become the lowest value among treatments, contributes to reduce yield up to 1.08 t/ha. Mahrup et al. (2005) reported rice production decreases in the South Lombok region which is dominated by vertisol due to flooding at peak of rainy season.

Table 1. Effect of different sowing dates on yield and yield component of Inpari-39 grown under dry direct seeded system in rainfed areas of Central Lombok, 2016-2017 WS

Yield component	Sowing date				cv (%)
	T0	T1	T2	T3	
Grain yield (t/ha)	5.58	6.20	6.28	5.20	20.23
Number of panicle/hill	368	448	500	460	25.75
Number of spikelet/panicle	110.05a	84.90b	88.33b	85.10b	15.70*
Percentage of grain (%)	58.10	58.30	58.35	56.76	12.29
1000 grain weight	25.90b	27.78a	27.27a	26.77ab	3.48*
Length of panicle (cm)	22.83	22.15	23.73	21.74	6.89

Note: Means followed by a common letter in the same row are not significantly by Duncan test at $\alpha=0.05$. T0 (sowing at 20 October); T1 (sowing at 30 October); T2 (sowing at 10 November); T3 (sowing at 20 November). *: Significant at 5%. cv: coefficient variation. WS: Wet season

Earlier sowing at T1 reduced number of panicle/m² and significantly produces the lowest number of spikelet/panicle. First sowing date at T0 produce the least number of panicle/m² that might trigger the highest number of spikelet/panicle, but significantly has the lowest weight of 1000-grains. Based on rice modeling by Amarasingha et al. (2014), it is better to sowing late but in line with the arrival of rain rather than planting earlier than the arrival of rain to avoid reduced yields at 34%.

Figure 2. Value distribution of spikelet number/panicle (a) and weight of 1000-grain (b) of rice grown under dry direct seeded system in rainfed areas at Central Lombok

Unlike yield, panicle length, number of panicle/m², and percentage of grain, number of spikelet/panicle and weight of 1000-grain were significantly affected by sowing date. In Figure 2, early sowing at 20th October (T0) was significantly produce the highest number of spikelet/panicle. However, the grain filling was less optimum leads to lower weight of 1000-grain where that value was similar to most delayed sowing (T3). There is a tendency that yields decrease when sowing was too early or too late. Despite pests and diseases, transitional period between dry season to rainy season causes water shortage at the later stages large due to climate fluctuations (Hayashi et al., 2018). Figure 1 shows that in early October 2016, rainfall was relatively low, so the newly sprouted seeds were very susceptible to drought. The main limited factor to rainfed rice is lack of water during sowing and the end of growth phase (Fukai et al., 1998). Kumar et al. (2016) reported yield reduction between 1.26 - 4.75 t/ha from its potential of 7.48 t/ha is due to drought stress during reproductive stage. However, if the crops are submerged before the age of 5 weeks it can cause a decrease in the number of panicles per hill and the number of grains per panicle, or increase the number of unfilled spikelet (Fagi and Kartaatmadja, 2002). Saturated soil is needed after age of 7 weeks to get high yields under direct seeded system (Budi and Suprihatno, 1994).

Plant growth

Additional information about plant growth is presented in Table 2. There was no significant different on plant height, number of tiller, and dry biomass weight between sowing dates, except the productive tiller. The lowest percentage of productive tiller that significantly different to other sowing date

was observed at T2 when the crop sown on 30th October (0.03 cm). The crop sown on 20th November (T3) produced the highest percentage of productive tiller (95.51%) but similar to T0 (93.31%) and T2 (93.31%).

Table 2. Effect of different sowing dates on plant height, number of tiller, percentage of productive tiller, and dry biomass weight of Inpari-39 grown under dry direct seeded system in rainfed areas at Central Lombok

Parameter	Sowing dates				cv (%)
	T0	T1	T2	T3	
Plant height (cm)	119.80	126.60	126.60	120.60	4.43
Number of tiller	19.80	25.20	26.80	24.40	25.43
Percentage of productive tiller (%)	93.31a	88.74b	93.31a	94.51a	3.07*
Dry biomass weight (gr)	63.65	76.41	88.27	92.69	32.10

Note: Means followed by a common letter in the same row are not significantly by Duncan test at $\alpha=0.05$. T0 (sowing at 20 October); T1 (sowing at 30 October); T2 (sowing at 10 November); T3 (sowing at 20 November). * : Significant at 5%. cv: coefficient variation.

Little different growth parameter indicates the tolerant ability of Inpari-39 to abiotic stress. In the direct seeded system, there is a radical change in plant growth due to changes in the groundwater regime from dry to wet especially 5-6 weeks after growing. Kato and Okami (2010) stated that modification on root system is important to adapt aerobic and anaerobic soil condition. Our results are in alignment with the finding of Bashir *et al.* (2010) who reported statistical different for each treatment of six sowing dates.

CONCLUSIONS

The better grain yield of improved rice variety that tolerant to abiotic stress occurred at optimum sowing date of 10th November. Inpari-39 is suitable to grown in rainfed areas under dry direct seeded system with grain yield ranged 5.2-6.3 t/ha. Although there was no significant different on yield, sowing date was significantly affected yield components (number of spikelet/panicle, weight of 1000 grain, and percentage of productive tiller).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research was funded by the International Rice Research Institute in collaboration with Assessment Institute for Agricultural Technology of West

Nusa Tenggara Province in project entitle “Climate change adaptation trough development of a decision-support toll to guide rainfed rice production (CCADS-RR)”.

REFERENCES

- Aggarwal, P.K., M.V. Venugopalan, S. Rani, A. Bala, and A. Biswal. 2008. Quantification of Yield Gaps in Rainfed Rice, Wheat, Cotton and Mustard in India. Global Theme on Agroecosystem Report no. 43. Patancheru 502 324, Andhra Pradesh, India: International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (36 pp.)
- Amarasingha, R.P.R.K., L.W. Galagerada, B. Marembe, G.L.L.P. Silva, R. Punyawardena, U. Nidumolu, M. Mowden, and L.D.B. Suriyagoda. 2014. Aligning sowing date with the onsets of rains to improve rice yields and water productivity: Modelling rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) yield of the Maha season in the dry zone of Sri Lanka. *Tropical Agric. Res.*, 25(3): 277-286.
- Bashir, M.U., N. Akbar, A. Iqbal, and H. Zaman. 2010. Effect of different sowing dates on yield and yield component of direct seeded coarse rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *J. Agri. Sci.* 47(4): 361-365.
- BPS. 2006. Nusa Tenggara Barat dalam Angka 2006/2007. Badan Pusat Statistik Provinsi Nusa Tenggara Barat (195-196 pp.).
- BPS. 2016. Provinsi Nusa Tenggara Barat dalam Angka 2016. Badan Pusat Statistik Provinsi Nusa Tenggara Barat (213-215 pp.).
- Budi, D.S., and B. Suprihatno. 1994. Time of flooding for direct seeded rice and reproductive stage moisture stress for transplanted rice. *Jurnal Agromet.* 1(1 & 2): 35-44.
- Eviati dan Sulaeman. 2009. Petunjuk Teknis Analisis Kimia Tanah, Tanaman, Air dan Pupuk. Edisi 2. Balai Penelitian Tanah. Bogor (211-213 pp.)
- Fagi, A.M, and S. Kartaatmadja, 2002. Gogorancah rice in Indonesia : a traditional method in the modern era. Proceedings of the International Workshop on Direct Seeding in Asia Rice System : Strategic Research Issues oand Opportunities, 25-28 January 2000, Bangkok, Thailand. 47h.
- FAO. 2015. Conservation agriculture. <http://www.fao.org/ag/ca/>. (Accessed 11 September 2017).

- Fukai, S., P. Sittisuang, and M. Chanphengsay. 1998. Increasing production of rainfed lowland rice in drought prone environment – a case study in Thailand and Laos. *Plant Prod.Sci.* 1(1): 75-82. DOI: 10.1626.pps.1.75
- Hayashi, K., I. Bugayong, I.H. Siregar, Joharnas, L. Wirajaswadi, L. Hadiawati, N. Agustiani, and M.E.Orden. 2018. Appraisal of rainfed rice production and management practices through case studies in North Sumatera and West Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia. *Trop. Agr. Develop.* 62(1): 43-54.
- Ismail, I.G., and S. Effendi. 1975. Cropping system research and development in Indonesia. <http://www.fao.org/>. (Accessed 11 September 2017).
- Kato, Y., and K. Katsura. 2014. Rice adaptation to aerobic soils: physiological consideration and implication for agronomy. *Plant Prod. Sci.* 17(1): 1-12.
- Kumar, S., S.K. Dwivedi, V. Prakash, K.K. Rao, S.K. Samal, J.S. Mishra, and A. Kumar. 2016. Rice breeding for drought tolerance under the changing of climate scenario. Springer Sciece. DOI 10.1007/978-981-10-2558-7_22
- Laing, A., C.H. Roth, D.S. Gaydon, V. Phengvichith, Sipaseuth, K. Thiravong, S. Vorlasan, and J. Schiller. 2015. Combining field trials and crop modelling of dry direct seeded rice to reduce production risk in Lao PDR under current and future climate. Proceeding of the 17th ASA Conference “Building Productive, Diverse, and Sustainable Landscapes”. 20-24 September 2015, Hobart, Australia.
- Mahrup, A. Borrel, M. Ma’shum, I.G.W. Kusnarta, Sukartono, J. Tisdal, and J.S. Gill. 2005. Soil management system improve water use efficiency of rainfed rice in the semi-arid tropics of Southern Lombok, Eastern Indonesia. *Plant Prod.Sci.* 8(3): 342-344.
- Pandey, S., M. Mortimer, L. Wade, T.P. Tuong, K. Lopez, and B. Hardy. 2002. Direct seeding: research and opportunities. Proceedings of the International Workshop on Direct Seeding in Asia Rice System: Strategic Research Issues and Opportunities, 25-28 January 2000, Bangkok, Thailand. Los Banos (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. p. 383.
- STAR version 2.1.1. 2014. Biometrics and Breeding Information, PBGB Division, International Rice Research Institute, Los Banos, Laguna.
- Wahab, M.I., Satoto, R. Rachmat, A. Gusnawa, dan Suhama. 2017. Deskripsi varietas unggul padi. Badan Penelitian dan Pengembangan Pertanian, Kementerian Pertanian.

Yasin, I., M. Ma'shum, Y. Abawi, dan L. Hadiawati. 2004. Penggunaan indeks osilasi selatan untuk memprakirakan sifat hujan musiman guna menentukan strategi tanam di lahan tadah huja di Pulau Lombok. *J. Agromet* 18(2): 24-36.